

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR MAKING MADMPS WORK FOR YOU

A GUIDE FOR LIBRARIES

webmgr@arl.org
bit.ly/mappilot

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A collaboration between the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) and the California Digital Library (CDL.)

As a librarian, you're always looking for better and more efficient ways to support researchers and research data management. Libraries serve as a hub, engaging with departments and information management roles across campus. They are uniquely well-positioned to initiate multi-stakeholder landscape analysis of research data touchpoints within their institutions. They can also initiate new solutions to facilitate widespread efficiencies and policy compliance. Improved research data management workflows and the use of maDMPs can help institutions address a

number of challenges and allow units with limited capacity to do more.

DMP Tool recently partnered with the Association of Research Libraries to work with a number of institutions, piloting activities to explore how maDMP integrations can be leveraged. The project revealed considerable potential for libraries to lead in developing new maDMP powered workflows to automate workflows, generate auto notifications, and coordinate resource allocation to facilitate smoother communication and information flow between units.

Benefits of maDMPs for your institution

01. Support for researchers

Libraries can leverage maDMPs to provide tailored support to researchers, including guidance on data management best practices, relevant policies, and available resources. maDMPs can provide further support in the reduction of duplicative data entry for researchers, and the creation of integrations that can automate support notifications linked to resource allocation. For example, you could build a system that passes information from the maDMP to campus computing units to prepare proper storage needs.

02. Grant compliance

DMPs are often required by funding agencies, and libraries can assist researchers in meeting these requirements, streamlining the grant application process. Many grants now require progress reports on data sharing, and having a living maDMP that is updated over time makes this easier to complete.

03. Resource efficiency

By promoting good data management practices, libraries can help ensure that research data is managed effectively and efficiently, maximizing the return on investment in research infrastructure. Through custom built systems integrated with maDMPs, resources can be centrally allocated and tracked, streamlining resource allocation.

04. Data stewardship

Together with other key departments, libraries can play a key role in promoting data stewardship, ensuring that research data is managed ethically and responsibly, and that it is preserved for future use. maDMPs can better feed into data storage repositories. Institutions can build efficient systems giving librarians opportunities to more nimbly advise researchers on data stewardship and keep track of data stewardship actions through updated plans integrated with workflows. Administrators can provide customized guidance to researchers as they write their plan to ensure best practices are met.

05. Increased visibility and impact

By promoting data sharing and reuse, DMPs can help increase the visibility and impact of research, leading to greater recognition for researchers and the institution. maDMPs enable linkage to related works, increasing visibility and impact of research even further. This increases citation and data-reuse, and can increase the chance of future funding or collaboration opportunities.

Recommendations

Establish governance and alignment

Initiate partnerships across libraries, research offices, IT, Information Security, and grant administration early. Pilot institutions found that when stakeholders worked together from the outset, they uncovered unexpected efficiencies, built durable relationships, and better aligned their vision.

Initiate workflow mapping with all stakeholders, conducting a gap analysis of current DMP processes across units, and identifying points where automation could reduce administrative burden.

Engage senior leaders with targeted messaging about how maDMPs advance strategic goals. Leverage case studies from pilot institutions to show examples of maDMP capabilities and frame the opportunity as a way to strengthen research infrastructure and create efficiencies in the research support processes.

Collaborate with Information Security, Research IT, libraries, and academic units to co-develop a campus-wide research data stewardship strategy. This partnership should define roles and responsibilities across the data lifecycle, including planning, storage, access, security, sharing, and long-term preservation.

Communicate benefits to researchers

Given time pressures on researchers, clearly communicating the benefits of maDMP use is essential to ensure adoption. Key benefits to researchers include:

- **Enhanced data organization and management**
maDMPs can help researchers plan how to collect, store, and manage data throughout the research lifecycle, ensuring data is well-organized and easily accessible.
- **Compliance with funding requirements**
The DMP Tool brings in guidance from both the funder and their institution so they can see what they need to follow while drafting their plan.
- **Improved data sharing and reusability**
DMPs encourage deeper consideration of how to share data with others, promoting collaboration and increasing visibility and impact of their published works.
- **Flexibility to update their plan**
maDMPs can be updated over time, reflecting changes in a plan, making it easier to fill out funder or institutionally-required progress reports on data management.
- **Time-savings and cost-effectiveness**
maDMPs can save time and resources by preventing data loss, duplication, and unnecessary effort, especially when integrated with other systems.

Stakeholder messaging strategy

In order to initiate institutional investment in maDMPs, it's important to define a clear stakeholder messaging strategy, given the nuances and complexities of challenges and benefits to different groups.

For faculty and researchers, time savings and reduced paperwork are going to be extremely important. Highlighting automated resource provisioning, and showing real examples from peer institutions may help ignite interest; it is also worth considering that researchers from different departments will likely have differing needs and funder requirements, so messaging may need to be adapted. They are also under constant pressure to increase publications and citations, which published maDMPs can help support.

IT and library staff may be more interested in interoperability standards. Demonstrating workflow automation benefits, alongside the incentive to proactively address data security concerns are also likely to be strongly of interest.

Showcasing improved tracking capabilities, emphasizing audit-ready reporting features, and connections to risk management priorities, will be useful in engaging administrators. Funder mandate compliance and resource reduction are also important to demonstrate.

Incentives and training integration

Incorporate information about maDMPs and the DMP Tool into existing training, consultations, and resources, rather than focus only on training about maDMPs alone. Consider using tooltips, snippets, and other methods to succinctly share information and reach people where they already receive grant and data management information.

Questions?

Find out more about maDMPs by visiting bit.ly/mappilot and viewing the resources created from the maDMPs Pilot.